
STRATEGIES FOR REDUCING MALE DROPOUT IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN ENUGU STATE

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Abstract: *The purpose of the study is to determine strategies for reducing male dropout in secondary schools in the six Education Zones of Enugu State. Two research questions and two null hypotheses were formulated and tested at .05 level of significance. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population for the study comprised all the 335 (295 and 40) secondary school principals in the public secondary schools and Science Technical, and Vocational schools respectively in Enugu State. No sampling was done because the population was small and also served as the sample. A structured questionnaire was used for data collection. The instrument was validated by three research experts. Data collected from the respondents' were analyzed using Cronbach Alpha. The overall reliability coefficient was .79, the questionnaire was administered and retrieved by the researchers with the help of four research assistants. Out of the 335 copies of the administered instrument, only 318 copies were retrieved while 17 copies were not retrieved. The data collected with the questionnaire were analyzed using mean (\bar{x}) with Standard Deviation (SD) to answer the two research questions. However, each of the null hypotheses was tested using t-test statistics at .05 level of significance. The null hypotheses were rejected when the significant level was less than .05 and were not be rejected when the significant level was more than .05 level of significance. From the result of the findings, it was concluded that; to a great extent innovative monitoring strategy and mentoring strategy assist in reducing male dropout in secondary schools in the six Education Zones of Enugu State. Comparison of male and female principals showed that, there was no significant difference in the mean response scores of male and female principals on the extent to which innovative monitoring strategy and mentoring strategy assists in reducing male dropout in secondary schools in the six Education Zones of Enugu State The researchers recommended that innovative monitoring strategy and mentoring strategy should be strengthened in secondary schools in the six Education Zones of Enugu State.*

Keywords: *Innovative Monitoring, Mentoring Strategies, Dropout, Secondary School*

Introduction

Education is the key to the production of human capital that drives the economy of any nation. The quality of the educational system today can to a great extent shape what the country will be tomorrow (Udoka, 2016). Formal education which is synonymous with schooling is as a matter of fact indispensable for national development, hence the indiscriminate expansion of the colossal investment in the formal school system. However, in spite of the huge investment in formal education in Nigeria, researches have revealed that school dropout rate seems high particularly among male secondary school students which calls for attention of all and sundry (Ikechukwu, 2019). It is worthy to note that secondary education is one aspect of educational institutions in Nigeria that is designed specifically to train and prepare students for middle-level services in both manufacturing and service industries. One of the objectives of secondary education according to Atuyi (2019) is the acquisition of both physical and intellectual skills which will enable individuals to be self-reliant and useful members of the society. It must be emphasized that secondary education in Nigeria is for six years duration, lower basic and upper basic. The two stages are both vocational and academic in nature.

The broad goal of secondary education as stated in the National Policy on Education is to prepare the individual citizen for useful living within the society and preparation for higher education (FRN, 2013). Thus, is seen as the most vital instrument of change and the bedrock of the nation's economic and manpower development. Obumnaeme (2018), posited that education builds on the capacity of the individual to acquire appropriate information, skills and competencies for personal survival, mental and social emancipation and the development of the nation. It is a vital tool through which individuals are empowered and a major instrument in national transformation. The issue of male school dropout and out of school children has consequently become a worrisome challenge to the federal and state governments of Nigeria. This is probably due to the realization of the social problems that could emanate from having a large population of school dropouts, who do not possess useable skills relevant to the labour market, and therefore, unemployable. Udoka (2016) stated that dropout rate from school is increasing. It is sad to note that it is not every child who starts secondary education that completes his or her education, hence they are called dropout.

Dropping out refers to a student quitting school before he or she graduates. It cannot always be ascertained that a student has dropped out as he or she may stop attending school without terminating enrolment. Obikwelu (2018), described dropout among students as a strong desire born in their heart to leave the school system before normal graduation period. In the same vein, Parker (2023), defined dropout as a kind of hunger-drive that pulls students out of their academic pursuit before the end of the programme. Parker, lamented that if this motivated propelling force is left unchecked, the aims, goals and objectives of the educational system will not be attained. It is estimated that 7.3 million students annually dropout of school in Nigeria (Omalu, 2022).

Reasons for dropping out are varied and may include seeking for gainful employment, poor grade, avoiding bullying, family emergency, depression and other mental illness, unexpected pregnancy and boredom from lack of lessons relevant to their desired occupations. Personal characteristics, home, finance and society were found by Ikechukwu (2019) as predisposing factors to school dropout among adolescents. Researchers like Okedara (2015), Akonobi (2019), and Ogunowo (2019), discovered the following factors that can instigate students' dropout tendency as: influences of bad peer group, parent low socio-economic status, and high cost of school, poor instructional methods and teachers' nonchalant attitude, unwanted pregnancy, among others. Understanding why students drop out of schools is difficult, because, as with other forms of educational achievement, it is likely to be influenced by individuals and institutional factors. Murithi (2021), lamented that even though a lot has been done by the government to reduce dropout among students in the society, the act seems to still be on the increase in schools and society at large. In view of this, Madziyire (2022), argued that in order to curb dropout among students particularly among the male secondary school students, strategies should be deployed. In the opinion of Charles (2022), many of the discipline strategies relied on by schools over the years are ineffective especially those that involve demanding, bossing, scolding, belittling and punishing as these tactics can keep behaviour partially under control only for a while. Charles added that they can produce detrimental side effect such as uneasiness, fearfulness, avoidance, dishonesty, and undesirable attitude towards learning, overall dislike for school and teachers, inclination to retaliate and for many the desire to leave school as soon as possible. Nwajagu (2022), asserted that reducing male dropout in secondary schools is a very important action of the school life, thus, requires a well thought out strategies. Nwajagu added that such strategies and methods should be non-punishment based. Charles (2022), posited that in reducing dropout among students in secondary schools, strategies to be adopted should be void of scolding, belittling, infliction of physical pain, canning or punishment on a student disobeying the rules and regulations of the school. Maduekwe (2017), noted that strategies in reducing male dropout in secondary schools should involve among others; the use of innovative monitoring strategies; and mentoring strategies.

Innovative monitory strategy involves the use of Information Communication and Technology (ICT) based monitoring strategy such as Close Circuit Television (CCTV) in monitoring all activities within the school environment. In the opinion of Aleke (2016) innovative monitoring strategy include, adoption of modern and contemporary electronic devices in controlling indiscipline in the school environment. Nwajagu (2022) noted that innovative monitoring strategy includes teaching of school rules and regulations to students as a subject or as part of civic Education. The idea is to let the students know fully what is required of them and the reason behind each of the rules; use of ICT based monitoring method such as CCTV in monitoring of examination halls and movements as well as the use of finger printing machines to monitor attendance and punctuality. Nwajagu further asserted that this method is less stressful, more reliable and difficult to beat.

It is unfortunate to note that lack of educational facilities has over the years posed a major challenge to secondary education in Nigeria. Ilo (2021) asserted that the available facilities in the Nigerian secondary schools today are inadequate quantitatively and qualitatively. Nkerenwem (2023) stated that only 40% of the Nigerian secondary schools are averagely equipped, while the rest 60% do not have. Nwajagu (2022) revealed that the inadequacy of facilities has put the school system at a disadvantage. Azikiwe, (2018), posited that monitoring measures are vital in the control of students' absenteeism and subsequent dropout in secondary schools. In the opinion of Maduekwe (2017), most secondary schools lack media, ICT facilities and this does not give students a practical knowledge and experience. Odi (2019), posited that the application of innovative monitoring strategy in the secondary schools is on a hard-line as the needed facilities are obviously not available, Odi, added that innovative monitoring strategy will go a long way in reducing male dropout in secondary schools if adequately adopted as well as mentoring measures.

Mentoring strategy have to do with assigning of each student to a teacher as guardian and making form masters move along with their classes as they progress in years. Aleke (2016) saw mentoring in education as pairing young people with an older peer or adult volunteer, who act as a positive role model. Aleke, continued that mentoring aims to build confidence and relationships, to develop resilience and character or raise aspirations, rather than to develop specific academic skills or knowledge. Heyes (2019) stated that mentoring is a positive facilitation of learning and development between a person with more experience, knowledge, or expertise in a certain field, and a person who is less knowledgeable or that is new to the field. Heyes, continued that mentoring strategy take on many forms and structures, with a range of objectives such as support for transition, academic supplemented instructions and social support. All mentoring strategy, regardless of structure, are fundamentally a transactional process of support underpinned by a mutually respectful behaviour. Uche (2017) asserted that part of the principals' and teachers' roles is to serve as models of positive behaviour, positive self- concept and respect for others and to establish importance of academic achievement. Ugwu (2017) asserted that mentoring has been part of the educational process over the years; however not strengthened as a strategy of reducing students' dropout. Onyeike and Nwosu (2018) noted that utilization of these strategies in secondary schools must be applied by principals who are the heads of the school. These strategies appear to have the potential to reduce male dropout in secondary schools. This is because they are devoid of tension and fear. However, what is not certain is the extent to which these strategies are applied in secondary schools and by the school principals particularly for reducing male dropout in schools. This is the thrust of this study. The study is geared towards determining strategies useful to reducing male dropout in secondary schools which is equally dependent on some factors such as gender and location. This constitutes the gap that this study intends to fill.

Utilization of these strategies in secondary schools must be permitted and directed by principals who are the heads of the school. Onyeike and Nwosu (2018), noted that principals are the uncompromising leaders of their schools as well as administrators in whose hands lies the future of the institution. Okoli (2015), asserted that the success or failure of secondary school programs depends on the individual principals' ability and leadership skills to maintain the school. Principals' behaviour according to Ngene (2016), normally encourages the subordinates to achieve and maintain the school standard by setting rules and guidelines pertaining to school standard. It is the duty of the secondary school principals to ensure that goals of educational policies and programs are realized. It is worthy to note that the goals of the educational policies and programmes can only be realized through a conducive school environment. Nwajagu (2022), asserted that reducing male dropout in secondary school is an effective tool for ensuring that goals of educational policies and programs are realized but however, depends on the leadership strategies of the secondary school principal which is equally affected by factors such as gender of the secondary school principal.

Gender is described as the biological sex of an individual in terms of being male or female. It has to do with socially expected behaviours of male and females. In Nigerian society, there are differences and inequalities in the assignment of responsibilities between women and men, activities taken, access to and control over resources as well as possession of some qualities (Adigwu, 2014). Ainabor (2020), who observed that the degree of principal's leadership performance is dependent on gender. Eunice, Selpher and David (2015), stated that there is significant relationship between secondary school principals' gender and effectiveness in school management. Alhourani (2013), observed that female principals are found to motivate students' interest in the school than their male counterparts. Manning (2014), showed that male principals pay more attention to school challenges than the female principals. An ex-post factor design study of 100 male and 100 female high school principals by Ikey (2023), showed that more female principals (60%) used mentoring approach to motivate students in schools. The observed difference is probably due to man's assumption of their ability to handle and deal with issues, unlike women who may not be prepared to deal with violent situations so they make adequate plans and preparations to prevent such occurrences in the school. The issue of gender has gained much attention with little or no conclusion especially as regards the secondary school principals in reducing male dropout in secondary schools in Enugu State.

As strategies such as corporal punishment has been proved to be counter-productive in reducing male dropout in secondary schools, it has become imperative that another strategy of decline in male dropout among secondary school students should be explored. It is against this background that the researchers are motivated to carry out this research on strategies for reducing male dropout in secondary schools in the six Education Zones of Enugu State. This constitutes the gap that this study intends to fill.

Statement of the Problem

It has been realized that male student's dropout in secondary school in the six Education Zones of Enugu State is on the increase. Male students seem to have little or no interest in schooling and their studies particularly in recent times. This is evident in the male students' behaviour disposition and regard for education which is nothing to write home about. As a result of male students' poor interest in academics, they portray different types of ill-behaviours among which include boycotting of lessons, watching and practicing of different forms of illicit sexual acts, drug abuse, violence, telling lies, confronting teachers and principals, vandalism, lateness, absenteeism, rioting, cultism to mention but a few. These ill-behaviours have direct effect on teaching and learning process in secondary schools and may not be efficiently controlled with the use of corporal punishment measures that have been adopted over decades which yielded little or no impact. Application of innovative monitoring (ICT) strategy in reducing male dropout in schools could yield productive results necessary to achieve school goals and objectives as well as checkmating mal-adjusted behavioural patterns among secondary school students.

Stakeholders in education have argued that since strategies such as corporal punishment for purpose of ensuring students' attendance and punctuality to school has not yielded the desired results, another strategy of checkmating male students' dropout should be explored. According to them, these strategies include the use of innovative monitoring strategies and mentoring strategies. This approach, according to these stakeholders has the capacity of reducing male dropout among secondary school in students more than any other approach. It is against this background that the researchers are motivated to investigate the extent to which these strategies can reduce male dropout in secondary schools in the six education zones of Enugu State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study is to determine strategies for reducing male dropout in secondary schools in the six Education Zones of Enugu State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. ascertain the extent to which innovative monitoring strategy assist in reducing male dropout in secondary schools in the six Education Zones of Enugu State.
2. determine the extent to which mentoring strategy assist in reducing male dropout in secondary schools in the six Education Zones of Enugu State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were posed to guide the study;

1. To what extent does innovative monitoring strategy assist in reducing male dropout in secondary schools in the six Education Zones of Enugu State?
2. To what extent does mentoring strategy assist in reducing male dropout in secondary schools in the six Education Zones of Enugu State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at .05 level of significance.

Ho₁. There is no significant difference in the mean response scores of male and female Principals on the extent to which innovative monitoring strategy assist in reducing male dropout in secondary schools in the six Education Zones of Enugu State.

Ho₂. There is no significant difference in the mean response scores of male and female Principals on the extent to which mentoring strategy assist in reducing male dropout in secondary schools in the six Education Zones of Enugu State.

Research Method

The researchers adopted descriptive survey research design for the study. Descriptive survey research design is that in which the researcher does not manipulate the independent variable to determine their effect on the dependent variables (Idoko, 2011). It is considered appropriate for the study following the description of census survey by Odi (2019) as the type of survey research design in which the entire population for the study is used. The design specifies how such data are collected and analyzed. The population for the study comprised all the 335 (295 and 40) secondary school principals in the public secondary schools and Science Technical, and Vocational schools respectively in Enugu State under the control of PPSMB and STVSMB. It is made up of 175 female 160 male principals in the public secondary schools in Enugu State. This is based on data obtained from the Post Primary School Management Board Enugu (PPSMB, 2025), and Science Technical, and Vocational schools Management Board (STVSMB). Therefore census sampling technique was adopted because the population also serves as the sample.

A structured questionnaire named “Strategies for Reducing Male Dropout in Secondary Schools” (SRMDSS), developed by the researchers was used for data collection. The instrument has two sections; A and B. Section A contains the respondents bio data while section B is divided into two clusters with 26 items, structured to assist the researcher in providing answers to the research questions that guided the study. Part 1, was on the application of innovative monitoring strategy with 10 items while part 2 was on the application of mentoring strategy with 16 items. The response format for the instrument was 4-point scale of Very Great Extent (VGE), Great Extent(GE), Little Extent(LE) and Very Little Extent(VLE). Each response option had a numerical value assigned to it as follows;

Very Great Extent (VGE) = 4 points

Great Extent (GE) = 3 points

Low Extent (LE) = 2 points

Very Low Extent (VLE) = 1 point

In order to ensure the validity of the instrument, draft copies of the instrument together with the research topic, purpose of the study, research questions, hypotheses, and the developed instrument were given to three experts for validation. Two experts were from the Department of Guidance and Counselling while the other expert was from the Department of Mathematics and Computer Education, all from Faculty of Education, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu.

The experts were requested to assess the relevance, adequacy, suitability and comprehensiveness of the items in addressing the research questions as well as the clarity of the instruction to the respondents. The initial 14 generated items were increased to 26 items as suggested by the validators, while barrel questions and grammatical errors were corrected as well. The validators' comments were used to draft the final instrument that was used for data collection. The reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach Alpha Reliability Coefficient to determine the internal consistency of the instrument. The instrument yielded a reliability coefficient of .89, and .69. The overall reliability coefficient was .79, indicating that the instrument is reliable and suitable for the study. The questionnaire was administered and retrieved by the researchers with the help of four research assistants that were properly briefed on the content of the questionnaire and its administration to ensure that the questionnaire is properly administered. Out of the 335 copies of the administered instrument, only 318 copies were retrieved while 17 copies were not retrieved. Data collected with the questionnaire were analyzed using Mean (\bar{x}) with Standard Deviation (SD) to answer the research questions. However, each of the null hypotheses was tested using t-test statistics at .05 level of significance. The analysis was done with the use of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The decision rule; real limit of the mean scores was applied, therefore, the upper and lower limits of the mean is as follows;

Mean scores from 3.50 – 4.49 Very Great Extent (VGE)

Mean scores from 2.50 – 3.49 Great Extent (GE)

Mean scores from 1.50 – 2.49 Little Extent (LE)

Mean scores from 0.50 – 1.49 Very Little Extent (VLE)

The null hypotheses were rejected when the significant level was less than .05 and were not be rejected when the significant level was more than .05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1

To what extent does innovative monitoring strategy assist in reducing male dropout in secondary schools in the six Education Zones of Enugu State?

Table 1: Mean Ratings and Standard Deviation of the Male and Female Principals on the Extent Innovative Monitoring Strategy Assist in Reducing Male Dropout in Secondary Schools in the Six Education Zones of Enugu State

N=318

S/	Innovative monitoring strategy	Male	Female	Overall	Deci
N	assist in reducing male dropout	N=155	N= 163		sion
	in secondary schools through;	\bar{X}_1 SD	\bar{X}_2 SD ₂	\bar{X}_G SD	
		1		G	

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1	use of Close Circuit Television to monitor students behaviour in classroom	3.3	0.4	3.3	0.48	3.3	0.4	GE
		9	9	8		8	9	
2	use of Close Circuit Television to monitor students behaviour in examination halls	3.2	0.4	3.2	0.42	3.2	0.4	GE
		3	2	3		3	2	
3	use of Close Circuit Television to record activities of unruly students	3.3	0.4	3.3	0.46	3.3	0.4	GE
		1	6	0		1	6	
4	use of finger printing to monitor students attendance to class	2.8	0.7	2.8	0.78	2.8	0.7	GE
		5	7	5		5	8	
5	use of finger printing to monitor students attendance in examination hall	3.0	0.7	2.9	0.78	2.9	0.7	GE
		0	9	9		9	8	
5	use of finger printing to monitor students attendance to other non-academic activities in school	2.9	0.7	3.0	0.79	3.0	0.7	GE
		9	9	0		0	8	
6	use of dormitory prefects to write confidential reports on students' academic behavior	3.1	0.7	3.1	0.77	3.1	0.7	GE
		5	7	5		5	7	
7	use of class prefects to write confidential reports on students' academic behaviour.	3.3	0.6	3.3	0.63	3.3	0.6	GE
		8	3	8		8	3	
8	use of peers to write confidential reports on students' academic behaviour.	3.2	0.5	3.2	0.58	3.2	0.5	GE
		3	8	2		3	8	
9	use of psychological testing equipment to monitor students' academic interest	3.0	0.6	2.9	0.68	2.9	0.6	GE
		0	8	9		9	8	
10	periodic head counts during assemble ground	3.3	0.4	3.3	0.49	3.3	0.4	GE
		9	9	8		8	9	
Cluster Mean/SD		3.1	0.6	3.1	0.6	3.1	0.6	GE
		7	2	9	2	7	2	

Note: X=Mean; SD=Standard Deviation; GE= Great Extent

From Table 1 above, the result of data analysis for research question 3 indicated great extent with mean points that were higher than the cut-off point of 2.50. The variations in the standard deviation of the respondents were insignificant and show unanimity in the responses of the respondents. The value of the overall grand mean was also high at 3.17. This implies that innovative monitoring strategy

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to a great extent assist in reducing male dropout in secondary schools in the six Education Zones of Enugu State.

Research Question 2

To what extent does mentoring strategy assist in reducing male dropout in secondary schools in the six Education Zones of Enugu State?

Table 2: Mean Responses and Standard Deviation of the Respondents on the Extent Mentoring Strategy Assist in Reducing Male Dropout in Secondary Schools in the Six Education Zones of Enugu State.

N=318

S/ N	Mentoring strategy assist in reducing male dropout in secondary schools by;	Male N=155		Female N= 163		Overall \bar{X}_G		Decisi on
		\bar{X}_1	SD	\bar{X}_2	SD	\bar{X}_G	SD	
		1		2		G		
11	assigning students to a particular teacher for guidance	3.4	0.5	3.4	0.5	3.4	0.4	GE
		6	0	7	0	6	9	
12	form masters/mistresses moving with their classes as they progress	3.3	0.6	3.3	0.6	3.3	0.6	GE
		8	3	9	3	8	3	
13	inviting eminent members of the society to speak to the students periodically	3.2	0.8	3.2	0.8	3.2	0.8	GE
		3	0	4	0	3	0	
14	sending unruly students to spend time with respectable members of the society	3.5	0.6	3.5	0.6	3.5	0.6	GE
		4	4	5	3	4	3	
15	assigning junior students to a particular senior student for guidance	3.0	0.7	3.0	0.7	3.0	0.7	GE
		8	3	7	3	8	3	
16	assisting students to develop positive self-image	3.5	0.5	3.5	0.4	3.5	0.4	GE
		4	0	5	9	4	9	
17	helping students to develop positive image of others	3.6	0.4	3.6	0.4	3.6	0.4	GE
		1	9	2	8	2	8	
18	helping students to achieve new relations with age mates of both sexes.	3.3	0.6	3.3	0.6	3.3	0.6	GE
		8	3	9	2	8	2	
19	encouraging healthy interpersonal relationship among students	3.1	0.8	3.1	0.8	3.1	0.8	GE
		5	7	6	5	6	6	
20	encouraging students to have weekly individual session with the school	3.3	0.7	3.3	0.7	3.3	0.7	GE
		1	3	1	2	1	2	

	counselor							
21	instructing form masters/ mistresses to hold regular interactive sessions with their assigned classes	3.4	0.5	3.4	0.4	3.4	0.5	GE
		6	0	6	9	6	0	
22	using audio visual materials to shape students' academic interest	3.2	0.7	3.2	0.7	3.2	0.7	GE
		3	0	2	0	2	0	
23	daily teaching of moral instruction on the assembly ground	3.3	0.4	3.3	0.4	3.3	0.4	GE
		8	9	9	9	8	9	
24	displaying good qualities for students to model after	2.9	0.5	3.0	0.5	2.9	0.5	GE
		9	5	0	6	9	5	
25	assisting students to achieve a socially responsible behaviour	3.3	0.4	3.3	0.4	3.3	0.4	GE
		9	9	8	8	8	9	
26	providing mentorship seminar program for students	3.0	0.8	3.0	0.8	3.0	0.8	GE
		8	3	8	2	8	3	
Cluster Mean/SD		3.3	0.6	3.3	0.6	3.3	0.6	GE
		3	3	3	2	3	3	

Note: X=Mean; SD=Standard Deviation; VGE = Very Great Extent; GH = Great Extent

Data presented in Table 2 above shows that the overall mean rating of items depicted very great extent with cut-off points above 2.50. The standard deviation of 0.63 shows that the respondents have homogeneity in their responses to the items. The overall cluster mean of 3.33 also showed great extent. This implies that mentoring strategy to a great extent assist in reducing male dropout in secondary schools in the six Education Zones of Enugu State.

Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in the mean response scores of male and female principals on the extent to which innovative monitoring strategy assist in reducing male dropout in secondary schools in the six Education Zones of Enugu State.

Table 3: Summary of t-test Analysis of Mean Response Scores of Male and Female Principals on the Extent to which Innovative Monitoring Strategy Assist in Reducing Male Dropout in Secondary Schools in the Six Education Zones of Enugu State

Variables	N			Sig. (2tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Decision
		t	df				
Male Principal	155	.091	316	.928	.03269	.35972	

NS

Female 163
Principal

NS= Not Significant

The data obtained from the t-test analysis in Table 3 shows that the t-value at 0.05 level of significant and 316 degree of freedom for the items is 0.091 with a significant value of 0.928. Since the significant value of .928 is more than the .05 level of significant the null hypothesis is not significant. This means that there is no significant difference in the mean response scores of male and female principals on the extent to which innovative monitoring strategy assist in reducing male dropout in secondary schools in the six Education Zones of Enugu State.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference in the mean response scores of male and female Principals on the extent to which mentoring strategy assist in reducing male dropout in secondary schools in the six Education Zones of Enugu State.

Table 4: Summary of t-test Analysis of Mean Response Scores of Male and Female Principals on the Extent to which Mentoring Strategy Assist in Reducing Male Dropout in Secondary Schools in the Six Education Zones of Enugu State

Variables	N			Sig. (2tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Decision
		t	df				
Male Principal	155	.156	316	.876	-.05767	.36908	NS
Female Principal	163						

NS= Not Significant

The result of data analysis obtained from the t-test in Table 4 shows that the t-value at .05 level of significant and 316 degree of freedom for the items is .156 with a significant value of .876. Since the significant value of .876 is more than the .05 level of significant the null hypothesis is not significant. This means that there is no significant difference in the mean response scores of male and female Principals on the extent to which mentoring strategy assist in reducing male dropout in secondary schools in the six Education Zones of Enugu State.

Discussion

The findings in research question indicated that innovative monitoring strategy to a great extent assists in reducing male dropout in secondary schools in the six Education Zones of Enugu State. This

finding is in line with Azikiwe (2018), who showed that monitoring measures are vital in the control of students' absenteeism and subsequent dropout in secondary schools. The finding is equally in line with Nwajagu (2022), who noted that the use of ICT-based monitoring methods is less stressful, more reliable and difficult to beat. Thus innovative monitoring strategy should be emphasized in secondary schools in reducing male dropout in the six Education Zones of Enugu State. Comparison of the male and female principals on Table 1 showed that there is no significant difference in the mean response scores of male and female Principals on the extent to which innovative monitoring strategy assist in reducing male dropout in secondary schools in the six Education Zones of Enugu State. This finding agrees with Ainabor (2020), who observed that the degree of principal's leadership performance is dependent on gender. Thus gender plays a significant role in principals' application of innovative monitoring strategy in reducing male dropout in secondary schools in the six Education Zones of Enugu State.

Result in research question two sought to find out the extent mentoring strategy assist in reducing male dropout in secondary schools in the six Education Zones of Enugu State. The findings revealed that mentoring strategy to a great extent assist in reducing male dropout in secondary schools in the six Education Zones of Enugu State. This finding agrees with Heyes (2019), who stated that mentoring is a positive facilitation of learning and development between a person with more experience, knowledge, or expertise in a certain field, and a person who is less knowledgeable or that is new to the field. The finding disagree Ugwu (2019), who asserted that mentoring has been part of the educational process over the years; however not strengthened as a strategy of reducing students' dropout. Therefore mentoring strategy should be constantly strengthened as a means of reducing male dropout in secondary schools in the six Education Zones of Enugu State. Comparison of the male and female principals on Table 4 showed that there is no significant difference in the mean response scores of male and female Principals on the extent to which mentoring strategy assist in reducing male dropout in secondary schools in the six Education Zones of Enugu State. This finding disagrees with Selpher (2015), who found that there is a significant relationship between the secondary school principals' gender and effectiveness in school management. The observed difference is probably due to man's assumption of their ability to handle and deal with behavioural issues, unlike women who may not be prepared to deal with such situations. Female genders appear to prefer adequate plans and preparations to prevent the occurrence of issues in the school.

Educational Implications of the Findings

The findings of this study hold implication for secondary school authorities, teachers and students. The study holds implication for the school authorities as the result of this study will find better means of reducing male dropout in secondary schools instead of the traditional use of corporal punishment which have yielded little or no result in reducing dropout in schools. The findings of this study will

serve as a guide to the school authorities on the best strategy to be adopted in school environment at each given situation while dealing with the issue of male dropout.

The study holds implication for the students who stand to gain more from the results of this study as it will serve as a guide to the students against reducing dropout and will help the students to develop self-esteem, assertiveness and adjustment in behaviour, in the hope of making them better contributors and academic efficient members of society.

The findings of this study holds an implication for the counsellors and teachers whom are saddled with the responsibility of assisting students with educational, vocational and personal social problems of which dropout is one in secondary schools. The educational implication of this study, therefore, provides secondary school counsellors and teachers with better strategies in reducing male dropout in secondary schools bearing in mind that, it appears that no none of these strategies have been adopted in reducing male dropout in secondary schools in the six Education Zones of Enugu State to the best knowledge of the researchers.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study the following recommendations were made.

1. Innovative monitoring strategy should be strengthened in the secondary schools in reducing male dropout in secondary schools in the six Education Zones of Enugu State.
2. Mentoring strategy should be strengthened in the secondary schools in reducing male dropout in secondary schools in the six Education Zones of Enugu State.
3. Deliberate efforts should be made at mentoring secondary school students by assigning a student to a teacher of his choice for mentorship.

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